

Los Baños and at Chuncheon (see figure).

Entries with long growth duration at Los Baños generally also had long growth duration at Chuncheon (see figure). But 12 entries had short growth duration at Los Baños and relatively long duration at Chuncheon, probably because they were photoperiod-sensitive and the days in

Chuncheon were long.

Preliminary selection for early maturity can be done at Los Baños and entries which flower in more than 70 days can be removed.

Indica varieties in the IRRI germplasm collection with growth duration of 94 days or less at Los Baños were evaluated

in Korea. Most of the 240 varieties tested had early growth duration but the long day lengths in Korea apparently delayed 8 photoperiod-sensitive varieties.

Hungarian 1 and Tinpakhia were the earliest, 20 days earlier than the short growth duration Josaengtongil at 21.2°C water temperature. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Fatty acid content of rice leaves affected by bronzing disease

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Iron toxicity or *bronzing* is a major physiological disease of rice in Sri Lanka's wet zone. Cytological changes in diseased leaves have shown that the accumulation of brown globules in chlorophyllous tissues is a characteristic associated with bronzing. The brown globules are weakly acidic.

This study showed that brown globules have an affinity to stains such as Sudan III, Sudan IV, and Nile Blue – an indication that the globules are fat or oil droplets. To further ascertain that the brown globules are oil, the fatty acid contents of diseased and of healthy leaves were quantitatively compared.

Plant materials of rice varieties BG34-8, BG11-11, IR2061-214-2-7-6-3, and H9 were analyzed. BG34-8 and H9 were grown in liquid culture; BG11-11 and IR2061-214-2-7-6-3 were obtained from the IRRI-Sri Lanka collaborative iron toxicity screening site at Padukka. To induce iron toxicity, ferrous sulfate was added to the culture medium. The varieties grown in the field were planted in replicates; disease incidence was observed only in some of the replicates. Leaf samples were collected from healthy and severely bronzed plants. Lipids extracted from the samples were processed and the methyl esters of fatty acids were analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography. All fatty acids were identified by retention times and peak enhancements

Total area of peaks obtained in leaves of healthy and diseased plants of four rice varieties. University of Sri Jayawardenapura, Sri Lanka, 1977.

Designation	Total area (mm ²) in	
	Healthy plants	Diseased plants
BG34-8	1457	2128
H9	2914	4022
BG11-11	1263	2097
IR2061-214-2-7-6-3	3432	4516

with standard solutions. Fatty acid contents were calculated directly by the peak-area method (see table).

The carbon number of the fatty acid that were identified ranged from 6 to 20 and the C-20 acid was found only in the diseased condition. A two-way analysis of variance revealed highly significant fatty acid contents in the leaves of diseased plants and highly significant variations of the fatty acid contents of different rice varieties. ■

Suspected ragged stunt disease in India

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Rice ragged stunt disease, first reported in the Philippines, was later found in various parts of Indonesia. The disease, which has been identified as caused by a virus, is transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Specimens showing the characteristic symptoms of the new disease were first seen at the Regional rice Research Station, Chiplima, in 1975 and later at the Central Rice Research Institute,

Cuttack. In 1976 and 1977, plants with similar symptoms were again seen, but the incidence was low. Transmission studies are being attempted, and varieties from the germplasm bank will be screened to identify resistant donors. ■

A new type of malformation in rice

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A new type of rice malformation was observed in the germplasm maintenance plots at CRRI in 1978 kharif. Affected tillers produced bunches of leaves that appeared like a fan; the tillers remained in the vegetative stage (see photo). At later growth stages, the upper portions of the tillers swelled, giving a false impression of an enclosed panicle due to the merging of the upper internodes and consequent crowding of leaves, covered by the outer leaf sheaths. In a few cases, incompletely emerged panicles with discolored spikelets aborted. Because the affected tillers had more internodes (7–10), their height sometimes exceeded that of the unaffected tillers. In other cases, a large number of shorter affected tillers gave the plants a bushy appearance. The leaves and internodes of affected tillers were crinkled and often twisted. Nodal branching was frequent. But vigor was not reduced in the vegetative stage. The malformed tillers often dried about a month after the unaffected plants matured.

Examination of the incompletely emerged and discolored panicles showed

Affected tillers. The arrow points to leaves that have remained in the vegetative stage CRR1, India.

large numbers of nematodes inside the spikelets. No such nematodes were observed in affected tillers that remained in the vegetative stage. The primordial portions of affected tillers had one larva each of some insects. That symptom was not observed in gall midge-resistant varieties such as Ptb21 and Ptb18.

Differences in varietal reaction to this malformation, as well as its cause, are being investigated. ■

Influence of nitrogen fertilization on development of sheath blight

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Sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is severe in several rice-growing districts of Tamil Nadu. A pot-culture experiment was carried out to determine the effect of nitrogen (N) fertilizer on disease development. Three plants of ADT31, which is susceptible to sheath blight, were raised in concrete pots in kuruvai (Jun-Sep). Levels of 0, 49, 99, 148, 198, and 247 kg N/ha

Effect of nitrogen on the incidence of sheath blight disease.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Mean disease index (%)	Increase (%) over control	Mean grain yield (g/pot)	Increase (+) or decrease (-) (%) over control
0	41	—	10.4	—
49	52	25	16.3	+56.7
99	62	52	14.5	+39.9
148	14	80	12.2	+16.8
198	83	103		10.8 + 4.0
241	88	113		10.2 - 1.9

^aDisease: SE = 0.8746, CD = 2.64. Grain yield: SE = 0.6801, CD = 2.05. Significant at 1% level.

(converted from kg/acre) were calculated and applied with urea. At all N levels, 62 kg P/ha as superphosphate and 62 kg K/ha as muriate of potash were applied. Half of the N was applied as basal, along with the P and K; and the remaining half was topdressed 25 days after transplanting. At the maximum-tillering phase, the crop was inoculated

with the pathogen by the straw-bit method developed by Venkata Rao and Kannaiyan in 1973. The intensity of disease development was recorded using the Standard Evaluation System. Increased N level proportionately increased disease incidence (see table). Severe disease incidence at higher N levels reduced the grain yield considerably. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in Orissa, India

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During 1977–78 kharif, a rice disease was observed, especially in late-planted rice, in the experimental fields of the Regional Research Station of Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima.

Diseased plants were stunted and leaves became ragged and serrated. Vein-swelling was marked on the outer surface of the leaf sheath. Flag leaves were small, twisted, and malformed. Panicle emergence was often incomplete and panicles bore mostly empty grains. Most of the tillers of the diseased plants were branched and produced many panicles. Flowering in diseased plants was delayed. Symptoms in the ratoons were similar.

Because the above symptoms are similar to those of rice ragged stunt disease, reported and described by K. C. Ling (IRRN 2(5):6–7, 1977), the disease is suspected to be ragged stunt, reported for the first time in Orissa.

Field observations on percentage of hills infected and percentage of tillers showing malformation and twisted leaves among 73 rice varieties from the

National Screening Nursery were conducted in 1978 kharif. Infected hills varied from 0 to 90% among varieties; malformed tillers, from 0 to 61%. Highly infected varieties included RP884-33-6, OR34-21, OR27-7, IET1444, Benibhog, IR28, and Cauvery. IR36, Pankaja, OR117-4, and ADT31 showed no disease incidence. Transmission studies to confirm the disease are in progress. ■

Chemical control of sheath rot disease of rice

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* is becoming serious in several high yielding rice cultivars. A pot-culture experiment on chemical control of sheath rot was conducted in pishanam (Jan-Apr) 1978, using the susceptible variety IR20. Eight fungicides – Hinosan EC, Kitazin EC, Benlate, Bavistin, Difolatan, Miltox, N.F. 48, and Daconil – at 0.2% concentrations were sprayed on the plants twice at 10-day intervals during the flowering stage. The disease incidence was recorded during harvest with the use of the 1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.